

Multivariate statistical approach to identify metal contamination sources in agricultural soils around Pb–Zn mining area, Isfahan province, Iran

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Abstract

The aims of this study are to evaluate the extent of toxic metal pollution in agricultural soils near the Pb–Zn mining area (Irankuh mining area, Isfahan province, Iran), and to find out their origins. A total of 32 agricultural topsoil samples were collected from the area under study and then, the concentration of toxic metals including Pb, Zn, Ni, Cu and Cd were determined by using atomic absorption spectrophotometry. The results showed that the mean concentrations of Pb, Zn, Ni, Cu and Cd were 51.80, 60.34, 35.75, 12.05 and 1.38 mg/kg, respectively. Various multivariate analysis including correlation coefficient analysis, factor analysis and cluster analysis were used to analyze the analytical data as well as to identify the possible pollution sources of toxic metals. According to the factor analysis and cluster analysis, 5 toxic metals were classified into three groups. The first group includes Cu, Zn and Pb; the second group includes Ni, and the last group includes Cd. To understand the current environmental status, the geoaccumulation index (I_{geo}) evaluation were applied. The average value of I_{geo} for Ni, Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd in the soil samples were obtained to be 0.23, 0.80, 0.96, 1.60, and 4.62, respectively. The results shows that the agricultural soil samples were moderately polluted with respect to Zn, Cu and Ni, moderately to strongly polluted with respect to Pb, and heavily to extremely polluted with respect to Cd.

Keywords: Source identification, Agricultural soil, Multivariate analysis, Geoaccumulation index, Irankuh mining area

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1. Introduction

Human activities including agricultural and industrial developments, have significantly changed the environment. It is due to the fact that such developments make use of natural resources, such as soil and water resources, and pollute them by harmful substances such as agricultural waste, industrial waste, sewage and etc. Concentrations of toxic metals are generally higher near the abandoned and active mines due to the discharge and dispersion of the mines' waste materials. In addition, soils are also contaminated with toxic metals by fertilization processes, industrial waste discharges, transport activities and atmospheric deposition. Toxic metals are one of the important types of environmental contaminants because of their non-biodegradability and non-thermodegradability. They are also accumulated in vital organs, including kidney, liver, and bones. Soil contamination, especially agricultural soil by toxic metals bring about major health problems for people through direct ingestion, dermal contact, diet through the soil-food chain, and the leakage of contaminants to the groundwater resources. Finally, other impacts of the existence of toxic metals in soil include the prevention of the biodecomposition of organic pollutants by microorganisms, destruction of soil fertility, and the decrease in crops quality.

Toxic metal pollution in soil and water resources in mine areas has been extensively studied in many countries such as Hungary, China, Spain etc. These studies show significant soil and water pollution by toxic metals in areas near mines. Despite the neutralization processes, the concentrations of Zn, Cd, As and Pb are higher than that of in a surface, which can be potentially dangerous for the environment. Moreover, there are higher concentrations of Cd, Cu, Hg, Pb, and Zn in the abandoned mine's tailing. Acid drainage and storm-carried dust were identified as the major causes of pollution dispersion. High resolution inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (HR-ICPMS) and diffusive gradients in thin films techniques were used in determining dissolved elements and speciation, respectively. A significant difference (with high correlation) between total concentration and the dissolved elements concentration of Cu, Pb, Al, Fe, Zn, and As in the sewage and in farthest downstream suggests the existence of a joint behavior between them.

The Irankuh mining area has been operational for approximately six decades and is one of the largest lead-zinc mines in Iran, with an estimated 10 million tons of lead and zinc reserves (Bahrami et al. 2014). The area surrounding the open-pit mines in Irankuh region has been

contaminated by the dumping of waste residues and atmospheric deposition, even though the agricultural soils are far from the point pollution sources. Although few studies have used to evaluate the toxic metals levels in soils around Irankuh mining area no systematic study has been reported on toxic metals in agricultural soils around this area.

The aims of this study is to (1) investigate toxic metal concentration in agricultural topsoil collected around Irankuh mining area; (2) identify possible sources using multivariate analysis and (3) evaluate the degree of contamination compared to pre-industrial levels.

2. Materials and methods

Study area and sampling

The Pb–Zn mining area (Fig.1) is located about 20 km southwest of Isfahan city in central Iran, between 32° 28' and 32° 37' N, and 51° 31' and 51° 37' E (Ghaderian et al. 2007). Agricultural soils were randomly sampled from the surface horizon (0-20 cm) and bulked together to form a composite sample. 32 topsoil samples were collected near the Irankuh mining area and transported to the laboratory.

Fig. 1

Geo-accumulation index (I_{geo})

The geo-accumulation index (I_{geo}) was used to evaluate soil toxic metal pollution by comparing current and pre-industrial concentration levels. The geo-accumulation index (I_{geo}) is defined by the equation (1):

$$I_{geo} = \log_2(C_n/1.5B_n) \quad (1)$$

where C_n is the measured concentration of the metal n in soil sample and B_n is the background concentration of the metal n in shale. Correction factor of 1.5 is considered to minimize the effect of possible variations in the background values due to lithogenic effects. The geo-accumulation index (I_{geo}) was split into seven classes as follows: Class 0 (practically unpolluted): $I_{geo} \leq 0$; Class 1 (unpolluted to moderately polluted): $0 < I_{geo} < 1$; Class 2 (moderately polluted): $1 < I_{geo} < 2$; Class 3 (moderately to heavily polluted): $2 < I_{geo} < 3$; Class 4 (heavily polluted): $3 < I_{geo} < 4$; Class 5 (heavily to extremely polluted): $4 < I_{geo} < 5$; and Class 6 (extremely polluted): $I_{geo} > 5$ (Kalender and Çiçek Uçar 2013).

3. Results and discussion

Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics of toxic metal concentration in soils in the vicinity of the mining area are presented in **Table 1**. The results of the summary statistics indicated that the mean concentrations of all toxic metals were significantly different from their corresponding reference values at Isfahan Province scale using a one-sample *t*-test ($P < 0.05$). The mean concentration of Cd (1.38 mg/kg) was much greater than its background value. The amounts of Cd in all 32 agricultural soil samples (100% of samples) are higher than that of background value. It can thus be concluded that the Cd contamination in soils surrounding mines is very serious and it was derived mainly from anthropogenic sources.

According to the results, the mean concentration of Pb (51.80 mg/kg) and its concentration in more than 68% of samples was significantly higher than the background concentration (28.10 mg/kg). This finding shows that Pb is moderately high enriching in majority area. For the Zn values in collected samples, the mean concentration of Zn was obtained to be 60.34 mg/kg, which is not significantly greater than its background value. However, 18.8% of the samples had Zn content exceeding the background value. So, Zn contamination should also be considered in soils around mines. High concentrations of Pb and Zn coupled with high coefficients of variation suggest the anthropogenic sources for these two elements. This is in good agreement with findings reported elsewhere.

Table 1

Data transformation

The parameters of skewness, kurtosis, and the significance level of Kolmogorov–Smirnov test for normality (S-K *p*) to the raw data, logarithm and Box-Cox transformed data were displayed in **Table 2**. Results indicate that only Cd and Pb passed the Kolmogorov–Smirnov normality test (S-K $p > 0.05$) before data transformation, and the raw data of Cd and Pb were used to further analysis. In order to increase the normality of other variables, Log and Box-Cox transformation were used. The normality of the raw data of Zn, Ni and Cu was improved using Log

transformation. Compared with Log transformation, the Box-Cox transformation significantly reduces the skewness values of data sets. Results showed that the Box–Cox transformed data sets of Ni, Zn and Cu passed the normal distribution test, and they were selected for further studies.

Table 2

Multivariate analysis

Pearson's correlation coefficients between all the Box-Cox transformed variables (with the exception of Cd and Pb) are summarized in **Table 3**. Lead had a significant correlation with Zn ($r = 0.642$) at a 0.05 of significance level, which may suggest a common origin for these elements. Also, copper has a relatively strong correlation with Pb ($r=0.582$) and Zn ($r = 0.382$), indicating that the Cu source of some locations is as the same as that of Pb and Zn. No significant correlations were obtained between Ni and Cd concentration and the concentration of other toxic metals.

Table 3

The varimax factor loadings for the first three factors are plotted in **Fig. 2**, which visually demonstrates the associations among five toxic metals in agricultural soils near the Pb–Zn mines. **Table 4** displays the rotated factor loadings, as well as communalities and percent of variance explained by each factor. The second factor (F2) accounts for 21.8 % of the variance and has strong negative loading on Ni. Finally, the last factor (F3) only included the element Cd, whose mean concentration exceeded 5.3 times higher than that of background value.

Table 2

The distance cluster indicates the degree of association between toxic metals. The lower the value on the distance cluster, the more significant is in the association. According to results shown in **Fig. 3**, five toxic metals were classified into three discrete clusters. The first cluster consisted of Zn, Pb and Cu and was mainly derived from anthropogenic inputs. Associations of

Zn, Pb and Cu are also observed in 3-D factor loadings plots (see **Fig. 2**). The second and third clusters include Ni and Cd, respectively. These results perfectly match with the weak correlation coefficient between Ni and Cd, and other three toxic metals (see **Table 2**).

Fig. 3

Geo-accumulation index

To understand the current environmental status and metal pollution extent with respect to natural environment, geo-accumulation index was calculated. The geo-accumulation index (I_{geo}) was applied to evaluate the soil quality. Figures 4 and 5 show the I_{geo} values for 5 toxic metals in the form of box plot and pie charts, respectively. The I_{geo} values of Ni, Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd in the samples range from -0.74 to 0.65 , -0.13 to 2.60 , 0.16 to 2.23 , -0.68 to 3.33 and 3.44 to 5.45 , with an average of 0.23 , 0.80 , 0.96 , 1.60 , and 4.62 , respectively.

Based on the mean values of the geo-accumulation index of the toxic metals, the order of pollutant accumulation level was $Cd > Pb > Cu > Zn > Ni$. The contamination of Cd in agricultural soils near the Pb–Zn mining area could be attributed to the large amount of industrial and agricultural activities. High Cd concentration in soil samples have also been reported in other Pb–Zn mining areas of the world including Poland (), Belgium (), Nigeria () and China ().

Fig.4, Fig. 5

4. Conclusions

In this work, the concentrations and sources of the toxic metals including Zn, Pb, Cu, Cd and Ni in agricultural soil samples collected near the Irankuh mining area have been studied. The concentrations of examined elements in descending order is as $Zn > Pb > Ni > Cu > Cd$. Factor analysis was performed on the data corresponding to five toxic metals and three factors were identified which control the variability in agricultural soils. Pb, Zn, and Cu content were associated in the first factor, determined principally by anthropogenic activities. Pb, Zn and Cu are probably originated from the mining activities and the use of agrochemicals or pesticides, and these origins are the main anthropogenic sources of these three toxic metals. The second factor, including Ni, can be considered as a natural component, and the variability of this element

seems to be derived from parent materials. Finally, factor 3 correlates with Cd and can be considered as an anthropogenic component. Knowledge of the sources, availability, and potential risks of toxic metals in contaminated soils is necessary for reducing health risks caused by toxic metal accumulation and selection of appropriate remediation options. This study evaluated a selection of toxic elements chosen on the basis of existing pollution sources located in the study area, which might not provide a complete range of information about the sources and availability of all toxic elements.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Table 1. Summary statistics for elements' concentrations in soils surrounding mine (mg/kg)

	Cd	Pb	Zn	Ni	Cu
Minimum	0.57	8.40	27.5	17.95	6.70
Maximum	2.31	135.80	181.20	47.03	28.20
Mean	1.38	51.80	60.34	35.75	12.05
Median	1.38	44.75	44.03	35.17	11.47
Standard deviation	0.45	33.66	39.26	5.30	3.61
coefficients of variation	32.61	64.98	65.07	14.83	29.96
Background value ^a	0.26	28.10	79.60	59.30	25.70
Percentage (%) ^b	100	68.80	18.80	0.00	3.10

^a Soil heavy metal background value of Isfahan Province [Esmaeili et al. 2014]

^b The percent of soil heavy metal exceeding the background value of Isfahan Province

Table 2. Skewness, kurtosis, and significant level of Kolmogorov– Smirnov test (K-S) of the raw, log-transformed, and Box–Cox transformed data sets

Data set	Parameters	Zn	Ni	Cu	Cd	Pb
Raw data	Skewness	1.83	-0.72	2.92	-0.08	0.72
	Kurtosis	2.49	3.62	12.79	-0.63	-0.37
	K-S p^a	0.00	0.02	0.00	> 0.20	> 0.20
Log-transformed	Skewness	1.20	-1.20	1.12		
	Kurtosis	0.47	8.12	4.47		
	K-S p	0.00	0.00	0.16		
Box–Cox transformed	Skewness	0.17	0.17	-0.11		
	Kurtosis	-0.272	2.15	2.28		
	K-S p	> 0.20	0.07	> 0.20		

^a K-S p is the significance level of Kolmogorov– Smirnov’s test for normality

Table 3. The Pearson's correlations between the contents of 5 heavy metals

	Cd	Pb	Zn	Ni	Cu
Cd	1				
Pb	-0.131	1			
Zn	-0.132	0.642*	1		
Ni	-0.195	-0.125	-0.125	1	
Cu	-0.272	0.532*	0.382*	0.160	1

Levels of significance: * $p < 0.05$

Table 4. Varimax-rotated factor loadings for the heavy metals

	F1	F2	F3	Communalities
Cd	-0.106	0.101	-0.988	0.997
Pb	0.897	0.097	0.031	0.814
Zn	0.825	0.182	0.054	0.717
Ni	-0.075	-0.952	0.094	0.920
Cu	0.733	-0.366	0.190	0.707
Eigenvalue	2.039	1.092	1.024	
Variance (%)	40.8	21.8	20.5	
Cumulative (%)	40.8	62.9	83.1	

Extraction method: principal component analysis

High positive or negative factor loadings are shown in bold